

First Step of Building an Arabic FrameNet (AFN)

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Abstract

In this paper we discuss our attempt to build an Arabic FrameNet (AFN). We describe our methodology of building a core of a lexical resource in Arabic that contains semantic and syntactic information of concepts and words, as a first step of building a complete Arabic FrameNet. We used "المكنز الكبير" lexicon to extract the semantic concepts and the related lexical units and frame elements.

Keywords: Arabic FrameNet (AFN), Frame Element (FE), Lexical unit (LU), Semantic Relations.

Introduction

Natural language processing applications often needs to deal with the semantic level of the language. Nowadays, many attempts have been clearly oriented towards building semantic processing tools and ontologies, such as *WordNet (WN)* [4], *VerbNet (VN)* [3], and *FrameNet (FN)* [1].

FrameNet (*FN*) is a lexicographic research project which aims to produce a lexicon containing very detailed information about the relation between the semantics and the syntax of concepts, to be used in many applications such as texts semantic parsing, automatic texts summarization in which we extract main and frequent concepts from the text being summarized, and also in machine translation. [1]

Actually, FrameNet has been constructed for several foreign languages such as English, Germany, Spanish, and Chinese. In this view *FrameNet I* [1] and *FrameNet II* [2] had been developed for English language containing all the needed information and many tools with the objective of annotating new corpora and tagging the lexical units of each sentence along with its props and participants.

Our goal is to build an Arabic FrameNet that will be of great use for Arabic language processing applications. We will present our work of building the basic structure of the AFN and our approach used for adding the concepts and its elements and units to our constructed FrameNet.

FrameNet Basics

The basic unit of analysis is the semantic frame, defined as a type of event or state and the participants and "props" associated with it, which we call frame elements (*FEs*). Despite the abstract and conceptual nature, we cannot define a frame without knowing the Lexical Units or *LUs* (*words in each of its senses – almost verbs*) that evoke this frame. For Example, in the frame "انتقام" we can have frame elements such as "منتقم", "معدّي", and "أدى" and the lexical units that can evoke this frame such as "انتقم", "تأر", "اقتصن", etc...

The most important step in this project is to define the optimal structure of frames and their elements, and to define their relationships with other frames. Those relations could link two or more frames together semantically. We mention here the most important relations:

- *Inheritance*: an is-a relation, in which the child frame is considered as a subtype of the parent frame. For example, the frame "انتقام" inherits from the frame "عقوبات".

- *Sub-frame*: a part-of relation, in which the child frame is considered as a sub event of the parent frame. This relation is used mostly in sequent actions for completing a more complex event. For example, frames in this order "اعتقال", "اتهام", "محاكمة", and "إصدار الحكم" are sub frames of the complex frame "رفع دعوة تجريم".

Constructing AFN

The basic structure of our constructed FrameNet is based on the analysis of the previous section. Our structure illustrates that Arabic FrameNet is composed of frames; each frame contains its elements as FEs, and verbs that evoke it as LUs. Frames are linked to each other with semantic relations. The structure allows the administrator of the system to define any type of relations to be used in linking frames together, such as perspective-on, using, precedence, part of, synonym, antonym, etc...

Fig 1.basic structure for AFN

The relations can be constrained with selectional restrictions that describe the character of the two frames being linked through this relation (see figure 1). For example, the selectional restriction on relation named "افتراس" is: "كانن" "حي" "يفترس" "كانن حي".

To illustrate the structure of AFN we present in figure 2, an example of the frame "انتقام", with its frame elements "عقوبات" and lexical units "الوحدات المعجمية", and its relation with another frame "عقوبات".

Fig 2. an example of the frame انتقام and all of its information

AFN Data and Work

To fill our FrameNet with data we have used two Arabic resources, the first resource was "المكنز الكبير" [7] from which we extracted the concepts and its lexical units that could evoke the appropriate frame. We manually extracted frames and added them to our AFN along with their lexical units and frame elements. Then, we link frames with each other by choosing an appropriate relation from a database which stores types of semantic relations that could be used to link two frames together.

Our system now works as a desktop application we present in figure 3 the main user interface of this application which shows frames and their related information. Meanwhile, we intend to build a web application that allows Arabic Internet users to interact with this FrameNet and suggest adding or updating frames on the Arabic language expert who will be the responsible of the system. This will make the process of addition and updating of frames more simple and effective.

As a step to expand the search options, we have linked our application with a morphological parser named KhojaStemmer [6].

In this view, we implemented the search panel in yellow in figure 3, so we were able to search for any word in the interface of the frame and to find its root at the same time, and other advanced search options.

Fig 3. The main user interface of AFN desktop application

Conclusion

We have constructed an initial version of Arabic FrameNet using the lexicon "المكنز الكبير"; we are filling this FrameNet with data (frames, FEs, LUs, and relations between frames). And we intend to develop a web application of it to enable internet users to add and modify the frames which let the FrameNet grow rapidly.

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